

MEDICAL SCIENCES

NORMALIZATION OF OCCLUSAL RELATIONSHIPS WHEN USING IMPLANT-SUPPORTED BRIDGES

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Abstract

To date, extensive clinical experience has been accumulated in the use of dental implants for dental prosthetics of various dentition defects. The success of dental implantation depends on a number of factors, both surgical and orthopedic. One of the orthopedic factors influencing the outcome of treatment is the state of occlusal relationships [6]. In this regard, it is of particular importance to align the occlusal relationships of teeth during implant-supported prosthetics with neighboring teeth and antagonist teeth in order to avoid increased oriented functional load on the implant, leading to disruption of the stability of the area of connection between the implant and the surrounding bone tissue.

Keywords: bridges, traumatic occlusion, implants.

A necessary condition for the dynamic restructuring of cortical and also cancellous bone tissue is the correct and uniform distribution of mechanical load during chewing, taking into account its magnitude and direction. However, implant healing and long-term preservation of a stable zone of connection between the implant and the surrounding bone tissue, capable of withstanding significant chewing loads, especially in patients with various occlusal disorders leading to the formation of traumatic nodes, remains an urgent problem [5,7]. Purpose of the work: to study the significance of correction of occlusal disorders by the method of selective grinding on the processes of osseointegration of peri-implant tissues. Material and methods We conducted clinical and radiological studies in 3 groups of patients at various stages of prosthetics using dental implants. The 1st group consisted of 8 patients using bridges supported by implants, the 2nd - 10 patients with single artificial crowns on implants, the 3rd - 13 patients using metal-ceramic bridges supported by devitalized teeth and implants. Patients of group 3 did not undergo selective grinding of the occlusal surfaces of dentures. Selective grinding was carried out in 12 stages (Bushan M.G., Kalamkarov H.A., 1983): 1) in the distal occlusion (static phase); 2) when the lower jaw moves back to the position of central occlusion (static phase); 3) in the position of central occlusion (static phase); 4) in anterior occlusion there is a static phase); 5) when the lower jaw moves from the position of central occlusion to the anterior occlusion (dynamic phase); 6) in lateral occlusion (right and left) on the balancing side; 7) when the lower jaw moves from central occlusion to transversal occlusion; 8) in lateral occlusion on the working side; 9) when moving the lower jaw from central occlusion to transversal occlusion on the working side; 10) elimination of supracontacts of the fangs in lateral occlusion (static phase); 11) elimination of supracontacts in other areas of the dentition;

12) smoothing and polishing of all ground surfaces of teeth. During the process of selective grinding, traumatic bumps were identified using articular paper. Correction of premature contacts was carried out in limited areas of enamel, on the slopes of the cusps to minimize trauma to the surface layers of tooth enamel. After each manipulation, the teeth were coated with fluoride varnish from Belak-F. During the period of selective grinding, all patients were recommended to brush their teeth 2 times a day with toothpastes that prevent increased sensitivity of the enamel. After selective grinding was completed, the tooth enamel was polished using fluoride-containing pastes to achieve a completely smooth surface. This manipulation was performed to prevent the formation of increased plaque deposits. The process of osseointegration of peri-implant bone tissues was monitored using targeted radiography [7,8].

Research results.

During a clinical examination, signs of occlusal disorders were revealed in patients: namely, traumatic occlusion, manifested by more pronounced exposure of the necks and roots of individual teeth, pronounced mobility of teeth I-II degrees in the area of occlusal trauma. Uneven deepening of the implant-gingival pockets was observed in 7 patients, and the implant-gingival sulcus, determined by probing from the vestibular, oral, medial and distal sides of the tooth, was observed in 4 patients. The examination was carried out before the start of selective grinding, at the end of all stages, and also 1 month after grinding. Selective grinding was carried out in stages, every 2-3 days, which allowed the patient to gradually adapt to changes in occlusion. The effectiveness of selective grinding of pronounced cusps of remaining teeth, as well as the occlusal surfaces of dentures supported by dental implants, was monitored by us for 1-, 2-, 3 months using radiography. At the same time, attention was paid to the degree of bone tissue at-

rophy in the area of dental implants and the X-ray optical density of bone tissue in the area of implants. According to X-ray data, in patients of groups 1 and 2, who underwent selective grinding of the occlusal surfaces of the teeth, after 1 month. After installation of the implant, the growth of newly formed bone took place, following the contour of the implant coils. There were no signs of inflammation. Selective grinding was carried out according to the mentioned method continuously during the 1st week of wearing dentures. In the images obtained after 3 months, the bone tissue had sufficient density and enveloped the threaded part of the implant. After 6 months, bone tissue formed around the implants, covering the implant on all sides. Clinical studies in dental implantation with immediate and early functional loading have confirmed the effectiveness of this method. In addition, the radiologically reliable lag in the processes of osseointegration of dental implants observed by us confirms the well-known opinion of a number of researchers about the close relationship between the processes of engraftment of dental implants and the standing of the occlusal relationships of the dentition. Due to the functional overload of the implant-prosthesis-bone zone, disorganization and resorption of the structural units of bone tissue, primarily trabeculae, begins with the formation of cavities that are filled with fibrous connective tissue [8]. Due to subsequent resorption of bone tissue, as well as its degeneration to the level of osteoid, devoid of a mineral component, microfractures of trabeculae and osteons are possible [9].

Conclusions.

Thus, timely and targeted selective grinding makes it possible to prevent the development of metabolic, functional and structural changes in the alveolar bone in the peri-implant area, which significantly improves the prognosis of orthopedic treatment of patients using dental implants.

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